

Studies on Spectroscopic and Thermal Behaviour of Neodymium Soaps

K. N. MEHROTRA^a, M. CHAUHAN*^a and R. K. SHUKLA^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Science (Agra University), Khandari Road, Agra-282 004

^bDepartment of Chemistry, R. B. S. College, Agra

Manuscript received 12 February 1992, revised 15 May 1992, accepted 17 June 1992

In recent years metal soaps have been used in industries and various branches of technology. The method of preparation and properties of lanthanide soaps have been reviewed¹. The present work has been initiated with a view to study the nature of bonding, structure, thermal and micellar behaviour of neodymium soaps in non-aqueous media. The structure of these soaps in solid state has been investigated by infrared spectra and X-ray diffraction patterns, and spectrophotometric result confirms the nature of bonding and micellar behaviour of neodymium soaps. The results of TGA have been used to explain the order of reaction and to find out the values of energy of activation for the decomposition process.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra of neodymium soaps (butyrate of caproate) have been recorded and compared with the result of the corresponding fatty acids. The absorption maxima observed near 2 650, 1 700, 1 440, 950, 690 and 550 cm^{-1} in the spectra of fatty acids are associated with the localised (COOH) carboxyl group² of the acid molecule in the dimeric state and confirm the presence of hydrogen bonds between two molecules of fatty acids.

The appearance of two bands of the carboxyl group corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate ion near 1 450 and 1 550 cm^{-1} in the spectra of neodymium soaps instead of one band near 1 700 cm^{-1} in the spectra of fatty acids confirms that these soaps possess ionised structure³. The results show that fatty acids exist in the solid state with dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between two molecules of fatty acids whereas M—O bonds in these soaps have an ionic character.

Spectrophotometry : The nephelauxetic ratio⁴ (β), percentage covalency (d) and bonding parameter⁵ ($b^{1/2}$) are calculated using the relationships,

$$\beta = (V_c^2)/(V_f) \quad (1)$$

$$d = [(1-\beta)/\beta] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$b^{1/2} = [(1-\beta)/2]^{1/2}$$

where V_c and V_f are the frequencies (cm^{-1}) for the transition in complex and free ion, respectively. The values of V_c have been obtained from the plots of optical density vs wavelength and are found to be 580.0 nm (17 241 cm^{-1}) for both butyrate and caproate. The value of V_f 574.5 nm (17 406 cm^{-1}) for free neodymium ion has been taken from the spectrum of an aqueous solution of neodymium ion. Since the values of β is less than unity (0.9905), it indicates that metal-to-oxygen bonding in these soaps has very small covalent character. The absolute values (+0.959) and $b^{1/2}$ (0.069) have little significance but they are very useful for assessing the relative covalent character. The small positive value of (+0.959) again confirms that bonding is ionic in nature. The smaller values of bonding parameter $b^{1/2}$ suggests that 4f-orbitals are very slightly involved in bonding in these complexes.

Optical density of solutions of neodymium soaps (butyrate and caproate) in methanol increases with increasing soap concentration (Table 1). The plots of optical density vs concentration of neodymium soaps are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration which corresponds to the CMC of metal soap (butyrate : 0.021M and caproate : 0.015M). It is suggested that these metal soaps are considerably ionised in dilute solutions and the anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles at CMC. It is obvious that

all properties which are connected with the number of particles in the solution will be affected by aggregating these molecules or ions. These micelles are in thermodynamic equilibrium with the unassociated metal ion Nd^{3+} and carboxylate ion $RCOO^-$ (where R is C_3H_7 and C_5H_{11} for butyrate and caproate, respectively) present in the solution.

axes of these soaps are somewhat inclined to the basal planes. The metal ion Nd^{3+} fits into spaces between oxygen atom of ionised carboxyl group without a large strain of the bond. On the basis of long spacings, it is proposed that the metal ions in these soaps are arranged in a parallel plane and these soaps have a double layer structure as proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi⁶.

TABLE 1—OPTICAL DENSITY OF NEODYMIUM SOAPS IN METHANOL

Concn. g mol dm ⁻³	O.D of Nd-butyrate	O.D. of Nd-caproate
0.004	0.040	0.032
0.006	0.059	0.050
0.008	0.075	0.066
0.010	0.095	0.080
0.020	0.185	0.150
0.030	0.270	0.225
0.040	0.350	0.292
0.050	0.428	0.370

X-Ray analysis: The intensities of diffracted X-rays as a function of diffraction angle, 2θ for neodymium butyrate and caproate have been recorded over the range of 6–80°. The interplanar spacings (d) have been calculated from the position of intense peaks using Bragg's relationship, $n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$, where λ is the wavelength of radiations. A large number of peaks arising from the diffraction of X-ray by planes of metal ion (known as basal planes) have been observed in the diffraction patterns of these metal soaps.

The appearance of diffraction upto 5th order for neodymium butyrate and upto 14th order for neodymium caproate suggest good crystallinity (Table 2). The observed values of long spacing for neodymium soaps (butyrate: 14.48 and caproate: 19.64 Å) are smaller than the calculated dimensions of butyrate (17.0 Å) and caproate (22.0

TABLE 2—X-RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS OF NEODYMIUM SOAPS

2θ	θ	$\sin \theta$	$\frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta}$	d	n	I/I_{max}
<i>Nd-caproate</i>						
13.300	6.650	0.115 8	6.651 6	19.955	3	0.25
18.055	9.028	0.156 9	4.909 1	19.636	4	0.06
22.475	11.238	0.194 9	3.952 7	19.764	5	0.33
27.088	13.544	0.234 2	2.289 2	19.735	6	0.05
31.405	15.703	0.270 6	2.846 1	19.923	7	0.05
37.002	18.501	0.317 3	2.427 4	19.419	8	0.09
43.168	21.584	0.367 9	2.093 9	18.845	9	0.05
46.558	23.279	0.395 2	1.949 1	19.491	10	0.05
50.828	25.414	0.429 2	1.794 9	19.743	11	0.05
65.504	32.752	0.541 0	1.423 8	19.933	14	0.07
<i>Nd-butyrate</i>						
5.958	2.979	0.052 0	14.835 0	14.835	1	1.00
12.271	6.136	0.106 9	7.212 9	14.426	2	0.28
18.739	9.370	0.162 8	4.735 5	14.207	3	0.22
24.878	12.439	0.215 4	3.579 0	14.316	4	0.07
32.882	16.441	0.283 0	2.923 8	14.61 9	5	0.06

Å) ions from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles. This suggests that the molecular

TABLE 3—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA OF NEODYMIUM SOAPS

Time (t) min	Temp. K	Wt. of soap de. composed $\left(\frac{dw}{dt}\right) \times 10^3$	$W_r \times 10^4$
<i>Nd-butyrate</i>			
4.00	333	—	5 515
6.67	373	596	8.936 4 919
9.33	413	695	7.449 4 820
14.67	493	695	4.738 4 820
20.00	573	845	4.225 4 670
21.33	593	994	4.660 4 521
22.67	613	1 441	6.356 4 074
24.00	633	2 236	9.317 3 279
25.33	653	3 180	12.554 2 335
26.67	673	4 422	16.580 1 093
28.00	693	4 820	17.214 695
29.33	713	4 969	16.942 546
30.67	733	4 969	16.202 546
36.00	813	5 018	13.939 497
41.33	893	5 118	12.383 397
46.67	973	5 466	11.712 49
52.00	1 053	5 515	10.606 0
57.33	1 133	5 515	9.620 0
<i>Nd-caproate</i>			
6	333	—	37 048
10	373	3 368	3.368 33 680
14	413	3 674	2.624 33 374
18	453	3 675	2.042 33 373
22	493	3 980	1.809 33 068
24	513	3 980	1.658 33 068
26	533	4 133	1.590 32 915
28	553	4 286	1.531 32 762
30	573	4 593	1.531 32 455
32	593	5 512	1.723 31 536
34	613	7 961	2.341 29 087
36	633	13 166	3.657 23 882
38	653	22 045	5.801 15 003
40	673	29 087	7.272 7 961
42	693	31 842	7.581 5 206
44	713	33 067	7.515 3 981
46	733	33 680	7.322 3 368
48	753	34 292	7.144 2 756
50	773	34 598	6.920 2 450
52	793	34 904	6.712 2 144
54	813	35 210	6.520 1 838
56	833	35 517	6.342 1 531
58	853	35 670	6.150 1 378
60	873	35 976	5.996 1 072
62	893	36 129	5.827 919
64	913	36 741	5.740 307
66	933	37 048	5.613 0
68	953	37 048	5.448 0

Thermal analysis: The results of thermogravimetric analysis of neodymium soaps (Tables 3–5) show that the final residue is the metal oxide and the weight of residue is in agreement with the theoretically calculated weight of neodymium oxide, using the molecular formula of corresponding soaps. A white crystalline powder is found condensed at the cold part of the tube surrounding

TABLE 4—FREEMAN-CARROLL'S TREATMENT OF THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA OF NEODYMIUM SOAPS

$\Delta(1/T) \times 10^3$	$-\Delta(\log W_r)$	$-\left\{\log\left(\frac{dw}{dt}\right)\right\}$	$-\frac{\Delta(1/T)}{\Delta(\log W_r)}$	$\Delta\left\{\log\left(\frac{dw}{dt}\right)\right\}$
			$\times 10^3$	$\frac{\Delta\left\{\log\left(\frac{dw}{dt}\right)\right\}}{\Delta(\log W_r)}$
<i>Nd-butyrate</i>				
3.003	0.258 5	—	11.62	—
2.681	0.308 1	2.049	8.70	6.650
2.421	0.317 0	2.128	7.64	6.713
2.028	0.317 0	2.324	6.40	7.331
1.745	0.330 7	2.374	5.28	7.179
1.686	0.344 8	2.332	4.89	6.763
1.631	0.389 9	2.197	4.18	5.635
1.580	0.484 3	2.031	3.26	4.194
1.531	0.631 7	1.901	2.42	3.009
1.486	0.961 4	1.780	1.55	1.851
1.443	1.158 0	1.764	1.25	1.523
1.403	1.262 8	1.771	1.11	1.402
1.364	1.262 8	1.790	1.08	1.417
1.230	1.303 6	1.856	0.94	1.424
1.120	1.401 2	1.907	0.80	1.361
1.028	2.309 8	1.931	0.45	0.836
0.950	—	1.974	—	—
0.883	—	2.017	—	—
<i>Nd-caproate</i>				
3.003	4.312	—	69.64	—
2.680	4.726	2.473	56.70	5.233
2.421	4.766	2.581	50.80	5.415
2.207	4.766	2.690	46.30	5.644
2.028	4.806	2.743	42.19	5.707
1.949	4.806	2.780	40.55	5.784
1.876	4.826	2.799	38.87	5.799
1.808	4.846	2.815	37.31	5.809
1.745	4.887	2.815	35.71	5.760
1.686	5.011	2.764	36.65	5.516
1.631	5.363	2.630	30.41	4.904
1.579	6.219	2.437	25.39	3.919
1.531	8.238	2.236	18.58	2.714
1.486	10.990	2.138	13.52	1.945
1.443	12.835	2.120	11.24	1.652
1.402	14.000	2.124	10.01	1.517
1.364	14.726	2.135	9.26	1.450
1.328	15.597	2.146	8.51	1.376
1.294	16.108	2.160	8.03	1.341
1.261	16.688	2.173	7.56	1.312
1.230	17.357	2.186	7.09	1.259
1.200	18.150	2.198	6.61	1.211
1.172	18.607	2.211	6.30	1.188
1.145	19.698	2.222	5.81	1.128
1.119	20.367	2.235	5.49	1.097
1.095	25.129	2.241	4.36	0.891
1.072	—	2.250	—	—
1.049	—	2.264	—	—

the sample, and it is identified as butanone, m.p. 39.0° and caprone, b.p. 228° in the case of butyrate and caproate respectively. The thermal decomposition of neodymium soaps can be expressed as

where R is C_3H_7 and C_5H_{11} for butyrate and caproate respectively.

It is found that the order of reaction for the decomposition of neodymium soaps is zero and the values of energy of activation from Freeman-Carroll's⁷ and Coats-Redfern's⁸ lie in the range of 6.29–7.88 and 7.00–7.25 kcal mol⁻¹ for butyrate and caproate respectively. The results show that

TABLE 5—COATS-REDFERN'S TREATMENT OF THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA OF NEODYMIUM SOAPS

Temp. K	$\alpha \times 10^3$	$(\alpha/T^2) \times 10^3$	$-\log(\alpha/T^2)$
<i>Nd-butyrate</i>			
333	—	—	—
373	66.64	4.790	6.320
413	77.71	4.556	6.341
493	77.71	3.197	6.495
573	94.48	2.878	6.541
593	111.14	3.161	6.500
613	161.11	4.287	6.368
633	250.00	6.239	6.205
653	355.54	8.338	6.079
673	494.41	10.916	5.962
693	538.91	11.221	5.950
713	555.57	10.928	5.961
733	555.57	10.340	5.985
813	561.05	8.488	6.071
893	572.22	7.176	6.144
973	611.14	6.455	6.190
1053	616.61	5.561	6.255
1133	616.61	4.803	6.318
<i>Nd-caproate</i>			
333	—	—	—
373	6.11	4.39	6.357
413	6.67	3.91	6.408
453	6.67	3.25	6.488
493	7.22	2.97	6.527
513	7.22	2.74	6.562
533	7.50	2.64	6.578
553	7.78	2.54	6.594
573	8.33	2.54	6.596
593	10.00	2.84	6.546
613	14.45	3.85	6.415
633	23.89	5.96	6.225
653	40.00	9.38	6.028
673	52.78	11.65	5.934
693	57.78	12.03	5.920
713	60.50	11.80	5.928
733	61.11	11.37	5.944
753	62.22	10.97	5.960
773	62.78	10.57	5.979
793	63.33	10.07	5.997
813	63.88	9.66	6.015
833	64.45	9.29	6.032
853	64.72	8.89	6.051
873	65.25	8.51	6.067
893	65.56	8.22	6.085
913	66.67	8.00	6.097
933	67.22	7.72	6.112
953	67.22	7.40	6.131

there is no change in the energy of activation with the increase in the chainlength of neodymium soaps.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Neodymium soaps (butyrate and caproate) have been prepared and purified as described earlier.⁹

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (methanol) on a Toshniwal CL 10A4" spectrophotometer. The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained over the range of diffraction angle $2\theta = 5$ to 80° on a Philips PW 1730 diffractometer using Cu-K α radiations filtered through a nickel foil. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out at

constant rate of heating under nitrogen atmosphere conditions in TG-S2 Perkin-Elmer instrument.

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Wiss. Z. Friedrich-Schiller Univ., Jena. Matb. Nat. rwis. Sreihe*, 1965, 14, 171 ; H. W. CHATFIELD, *Paint Manuf.*, 1936, 6, 112.
2. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Holden Day, San Fransisco, p. 39.
3. C. DUVAL, J. LECAMTE and F. DOUVILLE, *Ann. Phys.*, 1942, 17, 5.
4. S. P. SINHA, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 57.
5. D. E. HENRIE and G. R. CHAPPIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 49, 477.
6. R. D. VOLD and G. S. HATTIANGDI, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, 41, 2311.
7. E. S. FREEMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 394.
8. A. W. COATS and J. P. REDFERN, *Nature (London)*, 1964, 68, 201.
9. K. N. MEHROTRA, R. K. SHUKLA and M. CHAUHAN, *Acoustic Lett.*, 1988, 12, 66.